

An Analysis of Citizen Satisfaction with Services Provided by Antyodaya Saral Kendra: A Case Study of Sonipat District (Haryana)

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ABSTRACT

The old system of public service delivery is paper-based and time-consuming, which is inconsistent with present times and citizens satisfaction. The advent of ICT in governance improved the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery. The objective of this research paper is to examine citizens' satisfaction with the services given by Antyodaya Saral Kendra. The questionnaire schedule and observation method are used to obtain primary data for this purpose. Using a random sample method, total 90 respondents were chosen from Antyodaya Saral Kendra Kharkhoda, Gohana, and Ganaur in Sonipat district, 30 from each. The data was analysed with SPSS. For satisfaction, variables such as service sector facilities, cost and availability of services, corruption, employee attitude, transparency in rules and procedures, simplicity of process, and queuing system are considered.

KEYWORDS

Antyodaya Saral Kendra, Public Service Delivery, E-Governance, Citizen Satisfaction, Public Service

1. INTRODUCTION

To provide outstanding services delivery is an important pursuit for service providers that seek to create and provide value to their customers. There are several problems in the traditional public services delivery system such as delay in service delivery because of high level of administrative corruption and paper-based delivery system hence requiring high efforts of citizens to get services from public institutions this leads citizens towards the dissatisfaction. As a result, proper planning and successful implementation of planned delivery plans are critical components of a service delivery system. The Government of India adopted Information and Communication Technology in the public service delivery system and provides service through the Internet and takes several initiatives or programs like setting up of user-friendly web portals, Digital India Initiative and National e-Governance Program to strengthen e-governance in the country which enable the citizen to get service more conveniently. Use of ICT plays a vital role to provide hassle free services and reduce the burden of government as well as citizens. Introducing electronic public service delivery system, the institutions become more efficient and the delivery system is more transparent. This system is able to reduce malpractices in administration as well as nepotism, cost, service time and to establish better communication between citizens and government or discourage the culture of middlemen (Akinboade et al., 2012). This transformation has resulted in increased efficiency of administration with restructuring the internal operations and by speeding up the decision-making process. By providing government services electronically, this system reduces bureaucratic hindrance while enhancing the quality of service in terms of time, information, affordability and accessibility, and thus increased citizens' happiness (Singh, 2018).

1.1 SERVICE DELIVERY AND SATISFACTION

According to Fox and Meyers, service delivery is the provision of public activities, benefits, or satisfactions to residents. service delivery includes both the supply of physical public goods or the provision of intangible services. Putnam (2000) and Orren (1997) propose that the satisfaction of citizens towards the government is determined by both the public expectation and perceptions of the government. He discovers an unfavourable relation among public contentment and public expectations, but a positively related among public satisfaction and public perception of government performance. These other opinions that there are various factors involved in the satisfaction of consumers such as satisfaction of citizens are depending on the past experiences of services provided by the government and expectations towards the services among the citizens (Oliver 1997).

1.2 ANTYODAYA SARAL (*SIMPLE, ALL INCLUSIVE, REAL TIME, ACTION ORIENTED AND LONG-LASTING GOVERNANCE*)

Antyodaya Saral Kendra project is one of the prominent innovations in service delivery. This project has been developed for simplifying the service delivery to the common masses by receiving the applications of citizens at the single place and delivered the service within specified temporal. The purpose of government of Haryana was to restructure the state's public service delivery system; in February 2017, the administration made the decision to move toward the SARAL Shashan (Simple, All-Inclusive, Real-Time, Action Oriented, and Long-lasting governance), and the project was launched in June 2017 by chief minister of Haryana. On April 14th, 2018 on the occasion of Ambedkar Jayanti Haryana has made 181 schemes from 14 departments available to citizens of Haryana. On Good Governance Day, December 25, 2018, the Government of Haryana opened 115 Antyodaya Saral Kendra in all the districts. To accomplish total digitization of programmes and services, or to boost efficiency, decrease corruption, waste, and assure timely delivery of services with a citizen-centric approach, and save money within the state's service delivery system. The Haryana government developed Antyodaya Saral (online governance platform), a comprehensive online service delivery platform that incorporates the 550+ services or schemes of all departments without requiring direct contact with users or departments.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF ANTYODAYA SARAL KENDRA

The key objective of the Antyodaya Saral Kendra is to facilitate caseless, paperless and faceless service delivery to the citizens. This helps in transformation of service delivery system to achieve complete digitalization of services across the state and to provide quality services within the specified time frame. Its main objective is to standardize the service delivery system across the state and established a culture of openness to promote transparency in services. It facilitates to establish a better interface between citizens and administration to facilitate the suitable replies of queries, requests and inquiries.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper analysis the satisfaction among citizens towards services delivered by Antyodaya Saral Kendra of Sonipat district of Haryana. There are three Antyodaya Saral Kendra that are located in sub division level in Sonipat. The primary data are collected from three Antyodaya Saral Kendra's that are Gohana, Ganaur and Kharkhoda with the sample size of 90 respondents selected from those citizens who visited Antyodaya Saral Kendra by using an accidental sampling method. The responses are collected with the help of questionnaire schedule method of data collection. The collected data have been analysed with the mixed method approach. The secondary data collected from the various websites, research papers, articles and newspapers.

3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3.1.1

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	72	80.0
	Female	18	20.0
Age in years	18 – 30	65	72.2
	31 – 50	24	26.7
	More then 51	1	1.1
Education Qualification	Illiterate	3	3.3
	Up to Secondary (12 th)	40	44.4
	Graduate	34	37.8
	Postgraduate	13	14.4
Profession	Government Employee	8	8.9
	Businessman/Self-employed	3	3.3
	Student	51	56.7
	Private Employee	16	17.8
	Other	12	13.3

Source: Primary Data

3.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

The analysis of table 3.1.1 reveals that the majority of respondents (72.2 per cent) belong to the age group of 18 to 30 years, followed by 31 to 50 years of age group (26.7 per cent) and above 51 years (1.1 per cent). The male respondents (80 per cent) are more than the female respondents (20 per cent). The researchers also attempt to know the level of education of respondents. It reveals that 3.3 per cent respondents are illiterate and majority of respondents are passed up to secondary level, while 37.8 per cent are graduate and 14.4 per cent respondents are postgraduate. The table shows that the majority of the respondents (56.7) have students as a profession. The table contains information about the demographics of the respondents.

Table 3.2 Satisfaction About Providing Information at Centre, Responses of Complaint and Cost of Available Services

	Getting Information when Visit		Responses of Complaint		Cost of Available Services	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Fully Satisfied	18	20.0	7	7.8	15	16.7
Satisfied	53	58.9	16	17.8	40	44.4
Neutral	15	16.7	46	51.1	24	26.7
Dissatisfied	2	2.2	19	21.1	9	10.0
Fully Dissatisfied	2	2.2	2	2.2	2	2.2
Total	90	100	90	100.0	90	100.0

Source: Primary Data

3.2.1 SATISFACTION ABOUT PROVIDING INFORMATION AT CENTRE

Table 3.2 indicates the satisfaction of the information given to the citizens at the centre. It is found that 20 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 58.9 per cent of the respondents are satisfied. This means that most of the respondents are satisfied with the information of Antyodaya Saral Kendra. And 15 per cent of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Only 2.2 per cent are dissatisfied and 2.2 per cent

respondents are fully dissatisfied. From the above data it can be concluded that a high majority of the respondents are satisfied with the information provided in Antyodaya Saral Kendra.

3.2.2 SATISFACTION TOWARDS RESPONSE OF COMPLAINT/GRIEVANCE REDRESSAL

Table 3.2 indicates the satisfaction of citizens towards the complaint handling mechanism of Antyodaya Saral Kendra. Table 3.2 states that 7.8 per cent respondents are fully satisfied or 17.8 per cent respondents are satisfied. This means that more than one fourth of respondents are satisfied with the complaint handling mechanism. More than half (51.1 per cent) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. In all 21.1 per cent respondents are dissatisfied and 2.2 per cent fully dissatisfied this means that approximately ¼ of respondents are dissatisfied. It is concluded that the majority of respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied and the response of the satisfied citizens is slightly higher than that of the dissatisfied respondents.

3.2.3 SATISFACTION WITH THE COST OF AVAILABLE SERVICES

The data in Table 3.2 shows that 16.7 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 44.4 per cent of the respondents are satisfied. This means that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the cost of service paid by citizens at Antyodaya Saral Kendra and 26.7 percent respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Only 10 per cent respondents are dissatisfied with the cost of services and 2.2 per cent respondents are fully dissatisfied. It is concluded that people are satisfied with the cost of the services.

Table 3.3 Descriptive Statistics of Satisfaction Towards the Transparency in Service, Satisfaction with Rules and Procedure and Simplicity of Procedures

	Transparency in Service		Rules and Procedures		Simplicity of Procedures	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Fully Satisfied	3	3.3	1	1.1	7	7.8
Satisfied	16	17.8	35	38.9	48	53.3
Neutral	27	30.0	33	36.7	31	34.5
Dissatisfied	35	38.9	13	14.4	4	4.4
Fully Dissatisfied	9	10.0	8	8.9	0	0
Total	90	100.0	90	100.0	90	100.0

Source: Primary Data

3.3.1 SATISFACTION TOWARDS THE TRANSPARENCY IN SERVICE

Data of table 3.3 indicates the satisfaction of citizens towards transparency in services provided by Antyodaya Saral Kendra. As table 3.3 states that 3.3 per cent respondents are fully satisfied and 17.8 per cent respondents are satisfied this means that 21.1 per cent respondents are satisfied. 33 per cent respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with transparency in services. In all, 38.9 per cent are dissatisfied and 10 per cent are fully dissatisfied. It means that almost half of the respondents are dissatisfied with transparency in service of Antyodaya Saral Kendra. The culture of openness is not fully established in public services yet.

3.3.2 SATISFACTION WITH RULES AND PROCEDURES

Table 3.3 indicates the data of satisfaction with rules and procedure while taking service at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It clearly shows that 1.1 per cent respondents are fully satisfied and 38.9 per cent are satisfied, this means 40 per cent respondents are satisfied with rules and procedures and 36.7 per cent are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. 14.4 per cent respondents are dissatisfied and 8.9 per cent are fully dissatisfied. This means that 23.3 per cent respondents are dissatisfied with the rules and procedures of Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It is concluded that majority of the respondents are satisfied with the service rules and procedure while availing services at Antyodaya Saral Kendra and the rule and procedure are clearly defined by Antyodaya Saral Kendra.

3.3.3 SATISFACTION OF SIMPLICITY OF PROCEDURE

Table 3.3 shows the satisfaction of citizens towards the simplicity of process while availing services at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It shows that 7.8 per cent respondents are fully satisfied and 53.3 per cent respondents are satisfied, this means that 61.1 per cent respondents are satisfied with the procedure of Antyodaya Saral Kendra and 34.5 per cent respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Only 4.4 per cent respondents are dissatisfied and no response has been given in the category of fully dissatisfied. It is concluded that most of the respondents are satisfied with the simplicity of the process while availing the service, which means that the process is fully simple.

Table 3.4 Descriptive Statistics of Satisfaction towards Availability of Services, Waiting time of the Services and Level of Corruption

	Availability of Services		Waiting time of the Services		Level of Corruption	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Fully Satisfied	16	17.8	4	4.4	1	1.1
Satisfied	58	64.4	10	11.1	3	3.3
Neutral	10	11.1	36	40.0	8	8.9
Dissatisfied	5	5.6	35	38.9	35	38.9
Fully Dissatisfied	1	1.1	5	5.6	43	47.8
Total	90	100.0	90	100.0	90	100.0

Source: Primary Data

3.4.1 SATISFACTION TOWARDS AVAILABILITY OF SERVICES

Table 3.4 shows that citizens' satisfaction with the availability of services in Antyodaya Saral Kendra, 17.8 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 64.4 per cent of the respondents are satisfied. This means that 82.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the services available and 11.1 per cent of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Overall, only 5.6 per cent of respondents are dissatisfied and 1.1 per cent are fully dissatisfied. It is clear from the above data that most of the respondents are satisfied with the services available.

3.4.2 SATISFACTION WITH WAITING TIME OF THE SERVICES

Table 3.4 shows the data of citizens' satisfaction towards the waiting time of service at Antyodaya Saral Kendra, all 4.4 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 11.1 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the waiting time of the service and 40 per cent of the respondents are neither satisfied nor are dissatisfied. Whereas 38.9 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 5.6 per cent of the respondents are fully dissatisfied. It is concluded that most of the respondents are dissatisfied with the time taken for completion of service. Hence the system is not efficient and effective in the way of timely delivery of services.

3.4.3 SATISFACTION WITH LEVEL OF CORRUPTION

The data in Table 3.4 illustrates that the satisfaction of citizens towards any type of corruption such as corruption and bribery in Antyodaya Saral Kendra in Sonipat district. In all 1.1 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 3.3 per cent are satisfied or 8.9 per cent of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. While 38.9 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied with the level of corruption in Antyodaya Saral Kendra and 47.8 per cent are fully dissatisfied. It was surprising to the researcher that the high majority of the respondents are fully dissatisfied with the prevalence of corruption in Antyodaya Saral Kendra.

Table 3.5 Descriptive Statistics of Satisfaction towards Friendly Attitude of Staff, Service Area Facilities and Queuing System (Wait in Line/Long queues)

	Friendly Attitude of Staff		Service area Facilities		Queuing system	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Fully Satisfied	17	18.9	28	31.1	4	4.4
Satisfied	51	56.7	29	32.2	11	12.2
Neutral	17	18.9	4	4.5	25	27.8
Dissatisfied	5	5.6	12	13.3	41	45.6
Fully Dissatisfied	0	0.0	17	18.9	9	10.0
Total	90	100.0	90	100.0	90	100.0

Source: Primary Data

3.5.1 SATISFACTION TOWARDS ATTITUDE OF STAFF

Table 3.5 shows the satisfaction of citizens towards the attitude of the employees working in Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It is seen from Table 5 that 18.9 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 56.7 per cent of the respondents are satisfied. That means 75.6 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the attitude of the working employees and 18.9 per cent are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Only 5.6 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and not any response given in the category of fully dissatisfied. It reveals from the above data that a high majority of respondents are satisfied with the attitude of the working staff. This means that the behaviour of the working staff of Antyodaya Saral Kendra is good and fully cooperative.

3.5.2 SATISFACTION WITH SERVICE AREA FACILITY

The Table 3.5 indicates the satisfaction of citizens with service sector facilities such as drinking water, waiting rooms, toilets, etc. The data shows that 31.1 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 32.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied. This means that 63.3 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the service and facilities of the area and 4.5 per cent are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. 13.3 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 18.9 per cent of the respondents are fully dissatisfied, which means that 32.2 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied with the facilities in the service sector. From the above data it is concluded that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the facilities in the service areas.

3.5.3 SATISFACTION ABOUT QUEUES SYSTEM

Table 3.5 displays the satisfaction of citizens with the queue system at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It shows that in Antyodaya Saral Kendra 4.4 per cent of the respondents are fully satisfied and 12.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the queue system and 27.8 per cent of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. While 45.6 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 10 per cent are fully dissatisfied, it means that 55.6 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied with the queue system at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. From the above data it can be concluded that most of the respondents are dissatisfied with the queuing system. This means that there is a completely long waiting line at Antyodaya Saral Kendra when citizens visit Antyodaya Saral Kendra to avail any service.

4. FINDING

It has been found that majority of the citizens are satisfied with the services available at Antyodaya Saral Kendra as well as its simplicity of process, rules and procedure while availing services and cost of the services, service area facilities or information provided in Antyodaya Saral Kendra and high majority of the citizens are satisfied with attitude of the working employees at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. It has been revealed that most of the citizens are dissatisfied with the queuing system or a long waiting line present in Antyodaya Saral Kendra and the high majority of the peoples are fully dissatisfied with the prevalence of corruption in Antyodaya Saral Kendra as well as almost half of the peoples are dissatisfied with transparency in service of Antyodaya Saral Kendra and most of the citizens are dissatisfied with the time taken for completion of service.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Antyodaya Saral Kendra provide all the services and schemes of all 44 department of government of Haryana under a single place at tehsil and sub-division level. The main objective behind is to achieve the good governance in state and eradicates corruption from the government departments and promote transparency and provides quality of services in speedy way. To serve this objective and provide the services to every citizen in hassle free way the following suggestions are given by authors. It is found that the majority of respondents are unsatisfied with waiting time (time consuming in a service) of the services and wait in lines. Hence there is a need to increase the operating windows at Antyodaya Saral Kendra. In order to reduce the waiting line at the centre there is a need of an online appointment system should be set up by government in which a token should be given before the citizen arrives. The time and date of his/her arrival has been given in this token. To promote the culture of openness and reduce the level of corruption in Antyodaya Saral Kendra government should increased the budget of Antyodaya Saral Kendra because as they do not adopt other income methods like bribe. Some essential services are delivered by government at door of the citizens. To implement this idea government, create a toll-free number like Delhi government and a government employee delivered the services at their home like a food delivery model. Government should organise seminar, workshops ethical lectures and refresh training programs to employees of Antyodaya Saral Kendra.

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